

Anaocha Folk Tunes Collection and Documentation: Implications for Development and Modernizations

Offor Ndubuaku

*Department of Music, Faculty of Humanities,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt*

Abstract

This study was to find out how Anaocha folk tune collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations. The study adopted the descriptive survey design of correlation type. The study area was Anaocha Local Government Area. The population of the study consisted of populace bracket between the age of 40 year to 65 years in Agulu, AguluUzoigbo, Adazi-Enu, Adazi-Ani, Adazi-Nnukwu, Obeledu, Akwaeze and Nri. The main instrument of the study was a questionnaire. Face and content validation of the instrument was carried out to ensure that the instrument has the accuracy, appropriateness, completeness and the language of the study under consideration. The researcher subjected the data generated for this study to appropriate statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics and independent t-test analysis. The test for significance was done at 0.05 alpha levels. The study concluded that folk culture's adaptive mechanism, which was defined as the capacity to survive and thrive in changing circumstances, is a resource that maintains a person's identity, his or her connection with the community, meanings, values, stability, and life technologies. Folk culture forms the foundation for the regeneration and growth of contemporary communities in the midst of globalization and a spiritual values crisis. The study recommended that traditional songs cannot operate successfully in Anaocha villages until a system for training a new generation of performers and spectators is developed, as well as the resuscitation of the old environment of the listener and performer via the concept of co-creation.

Keywords: Music; Folk Tunes; Collection; Documentation; Development; Modernizations etc.

Introduction

The journey to knowing global and national cultural values should begin with native songs, native language, and native nature paintings and progress to understanding the art of one's immediate neighbors and world culture (Hasanov, 2016; Tleuova, Baltymova, Niyazova, & Tektigul, 2016). Each culture has something unique to offer, such as the quality of the nation's spiritual life, which has been gathered through ages and is expressed in certain traditions and ideals. Many aspects of ethnic group life (instruments and manufacturing processes, decorum standards, traditional clothing, and so on) lose their national color over time, leaving only art, particularly musical art, to preserve ethnic identity even in the face of foreign cultural influences. As a result of the shrinking of ethnic distinctiveness in culture, folk songs now serve a critical role in defining national identity (Kokumbaeva, 2012). The most prevalent genre of traditional music, a folk song is the result of a collective oral tradition that exists in numerous variations and transmits the identity of communities and reflects their thinking.

Folk songs are sung by ordinary people at work or at social gatherings. The fact that these songs are part of oral tradition is one of their most distinguishing features. Rather of learning from written sources such as books, the melodies and words are learnt via imitation and participation. Changes to the melodies occur throughout this oral transmission, resulting in groupings ('tune families') with more or less similar tunes.

Folk music is passed down the generations, and the best way to understand its history is to look at how it relates to other types of music. Many folk songs passed down the generations have been linked to literary sources, many of which are centuries old. In numerous ways, folk music and mainstream music are intertwined. Folk music traditions or vestiges thereof, exist in societies that have established popular music. Partially duplicating repertoires and styles implies such cross-fertilization that a song may be classified as both folk and popular. Folk and popular music are not two distinct bodies of music, but rather two points on a musical continuum. Folk music has steadily become more like popular music, created by professionals and broadcast via mass media for consumption by an urban, nonparticipating mass audience, much as popular music has become an important marker of ethnicity and country.

The pleasure that music brings to the human mind and spirit, on the other hand, is widely acknowledged. Of all the numerous arts, it is the most extensively practiced and accessible. It is widely accessible and linked with amusement and relaxation, both of which have significant implications for a country's social and economic growth. Music tourism and cultural music bring in a lot of money for certain nations. The simplicity of current technology has enabled the export of high-quality music, opening up a larger market for artists and their work. Nations to increase their revenue. Nigeria's diverse cultural music and dance is a big asset that may earn cash if exported. Despite the large sums of money that may be made from Nigeria's diverse ethnic music, the potentials (artists) have never been fully realized. Music education in Nigeria has flawed educational policies and implementation methodologies; as a result, music education should be scrutinized closely in order to bring forth the benefits and prospects contained in the art to the country.

Traditional music is being pushed out of a variety of popular cultural strata, and this is not an exaggeration. According to Olukoya (2015), there is a need to coordinate cultural policy actions in order to promote traditional music via a variety of cultural initiatives, innovative ways of teaching professional artists, mass media, TV, and radio. This dilemma will not be solved until smart management and marketing become public mediators between culture and society, government and culture, spiritual worlds of reproduction and consumption of art riches, past history and modern creative activity. Folk melodies have a great deal of potential for adapting to contemporary perceptions and laying the groundwork for the formation and modernisation of new musical cultures. Mr. Davidson (2013). Ethnic stage music, which satisfies a wide range of spiritual needs in the population, has emerged as a significant cultural factor that cannot be overlooked; on the other hand, it has emerged as a curious indicator of rapidly changing global and regional processes such as mass culture enforcement, individualization, and, at the same time, resistance to these processes by ethnic preferences (Najdorf, 2011). As a result of the development of folklore, new forms of performing song folklore have emerged, which mix traditional folk singing with parts of contemporary art that adhere to stage regulations. Pop performers are turning to folk tunes for inspiration, reworking them for a new audience. As a result, the old strata of folk songs are translated into a current musical language, making the archaic substance of folk song intelligible to a modern audience. Folk traditions, which are vivid representations of national style, are so perpetuated.

However, the growing demand for cultural Europeanization is having a negative impact on the Anaocha community's traditional music. As a result, attempts are being made to

modernize traditional music and its motivations. This has the potential to harm cultural heritage, thus it is critical to develop appreciation for folk music as well as national assets.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine Anaocha folk tunes collection and documentation and its implications for development and modernizations. The specific objective of the study is:

1. To examine the how folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities
2. What are the challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities

Research Questions

The study shall answer the following questions

1. How does folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities
2. What are the challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities

Research Methodology

Research Design

The survey method was utilized for this study. This approach was considered most appropriate because it helped the researcher to describe, examine, record, analyze and interpret the variables that were found in the study. It is also useful because of the relatively large population from which the information was collected.

Area of study

Anaocha Local Government Area is one of the twenty-one Local Government Areas that make up the present Anambra State. Geographically, it is bounded in the North by Awka South Local Government Area, in the East by Aguata Local Government Area, in the West by Njikoka Local Government Area, and in the South by Umuawulu Local Government Area.

Source of Data

The data of the research are of two kinds; primary and secondary data. The following sources provided the information which is: Textbooks, journals, magazine and unpublished articles; Research and project reports in a related field.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of populace bracket between the age of 40 year to 81 years and above in Agulu, AguluUzoigbo, Adazi-Enu, Adazi-Ani, Adazi-Nnukwu, Obeledu, Akwaeze and Nri.

Sampling and Sample Size

The Sample sizes of 383 respondents were selected for the study area. The sample size was statistically determined using the sample fraction.

Data Collection Instrument and Validation

The questionnaire was employed as the study's research tool. The questionnaire was used to collect data on the independent and dependent variables reported in sections A and B. Section A assessed the respondents' demographic data such as name, gender, age, educational qualification, and marital status, whereas Section B measured the independent variables. The research used the Likert (1932) scale.

Techniques of Data Analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using independent t-test analysis.

Data Presentation and Analyses

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by sex

Sex	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
MALE	194	50.65
FEMALE	183	47.78
Total	383	100

Table 1 show that one hundred ninety four (194) respondents representing 50.65% of the sample population were male while one hundred and eighty three (183) respondents representing 47.78% of the population were female.

Table 2: Age Distribution

Age	No. of respondents	% of Percentage
40-50	106	27.67
51-60	77	20.10
61-70	56	14.62
71-80	88	22.97
81 and above	56	14.62
Total	383	100

Table 2 shows that hundred and six (106) respondents representing 27.67% of the sample were between the age bracket of 40 – 50 years, seventy seven (77) respondents each representing 20.10% were between the age bracket of 51 – 60 years, fifty six of the respondents representing 14.62% were 17% were 61 – 70 years respectively, also eighty eight (88) respondents representing 22.97% of the sample were between the age limit of 71 – 80 years and fifty six (56) respondents representing 14.62% were within the age limit of 81 and above years.

Table 3: Marital Status Distribution

Status	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Single	158	41.25
Married	134	34.98
Divorced	55	14.36
Widow/Widowers	36	9.39
Total	383	100

Table 3 above shows that one hundred and fifty eight (158) respondents representing 41.25% of the sample were single, one hundred thirty four (134) respondents representing 34.98% of the

sample were married, only fifty five (55) respondents representing 14.36% of the sample were divorced as well as only thirty six (36) respondents representing 9.39%

Table 4: Educational Qualification Distribution

Qualification respondents	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
WAEC/NECO	162	42.29
OND	101	26.37
HND/BSC	53	13.83
MSC	21	5.48
PHD	46	12.01
Total	383	100

Table 4 shows that one hundred and sixty two (162) respondents representing 42.29% of the sample were WAEC/NECO holders, one hundred and one (101) respondents representing 26.37% were OND/NCE certificate holders; fifty three (53) respondents representing 13.83% were holders of HND/BSC certificates holders, while twenty one (21) respondents representing 5.48% were MSC certificate holders and only forty six (46) respondents representing 12.01% of the population were PHD holders.

Answering of Research Questions

Research Question One

How folk tunes collection and documentation does promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities?

Table 5: percentage analysis of folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities

Extent	Frequency	Percentage
Very high extent	122	31.85
High extent	77	20.10
Low extent	96	25.06
Very low extent	88	22.97
Total	383	100

The percentage study of the influence of Fulani herdsmen and farmers problem on the level of food availability in Nigeria is shown in Table 1. The table also shows that folk songs collecting and documenting encourages development and modernization in Anaocha communities. As a consequence, the research topic becomes noteworthy as a result of the outcome.

Research Question Two

What are the challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities.

Table 6: percentage analysis of challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities

Extent	Frequency	Percentage
Very high extent	137	35.77

High extent	89	23.23
Low extent	78	20.36
Very low extent	79	20.62
Total	383	100

The above table 6 present the percentage analysis of challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities. Therefore, the result causes the research question to be significant.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant different of folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities

Table 7

Independent t-test analysis of There is no significant different of folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities

				Variable
N	X	SD	t	
-----				High
234	12.01	1.30		21.45*

Low	149	15.15	0.71	

***Significant at 0.05 level; df= 381; N= 383; critical t-value = 1.96**

The above table 7 presents the obtained t-value as (21.45). This value was tested for significance by comparing it with the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 level with 381 degree of freedom. The obtained t-value (21.45) was greater than the critical t-value (1.96). Hence, the result was significant. The result therefore means that there is significant different of folk tunes collection and documentation promotes development and modernizations in Anaocha communities

Hypothesis two

There is no significant challenge of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities

Table 8

Independent t-test analysis of challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities

Variable	N	X	SD	t
-----				High
201	12.07	1.34		18.31*

Low	191	15.00	1.09	

***Significant at 0.05 level; df= 381; N= 383; critical t-value = 1.96**

The above table 7 presents the obtained t-value as (18.31). This value was tested for significance by comparing it with the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 levels with 381 degree of freedom. The obtained t-value (18.31) was greater than the critical t-value (1.96). Hence, the result was significant. The result therefore means that challenges of folk tunes collection and documentation in Anaocha communities.

Discussion of the Findings

Table 6 shows that the computed t-value (21.45) was more than the crucial t-value (1.96) at 0.05 levels with 381 degrees of freedom, indicating that the data analysis was significant. This means that there is a major difference in how folk songs collecting and documentation supports Anaocha community growth and modernisation. The null hypothesis was rejected due to the importance of the finding, whereas the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

Table 7 shows that the computed t-value (18.31) was more than the crucial t-value (1.96) at 0.05 levels with 381 degrees of freedom, indicating that the data analysis was significant. This finding suggests that collecting and documenting folk songs in Anaocha villages is a considerable problem. The null hypothesis was rejected due to the importance of the finding, whereas the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

Conclusion

Folk culture's adaptive mechanism, which was defined as the capacity to survive and thrive in changing circumstances, is a resource that maintains a person's identity, his or her connection with the community, meanings, values, stability, and life technologies. Folk culture forms the foundation for the regeneration and growth of contemporary communities in the midst of globalization and a spiritual values crisis.

Folk culture is now in demand by society as a genuine and useful aspect in society's growth and modernisation. Evening parties are held in honor of well-known composers. The evolution of Anaocha song revival is influenced by competitions, festivals, and anniversaries. Song tradition exists in current society; it evolves and is studied as part of folk culture, serving as a means of not only comprehending and reflecting reality, but also of harmonizing the world-man connection.

Recommendations

Traditional songs cannot operate successfully in Anaocha villages until a system for training a new generation of performers and spectators is developed, as well as the resuscitation of the old environment of the listener and performer via the concept of co-creation. The assistance of government entities capable of organizing large-scale cultural events devoted to traditional music is also required. In general, traditional music is a cultural legacy that encompasses the nation's history and customs. Modern folk music is becoming a national asset that highlights the Anaocha people's uniqueness.

References

Davidson, J. W. (2013). The main thing is uniqueness. Visual perception of performance manner of solo musicians. *Psychology of Music.*, (21), 101–113.

Hasanov, E. L. (2016). Innovative basis of research of technologic features of some craftsmanship traditions of Ganja (On the sample of carpets of XIX century). *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 11(14), 6704–6714.

Kokumbaeva, B. D. (2012). *Tengrian art culturology*. (p. 167).

Najdorf, M. (2011). On peculiarities of musical culture of mass media-space.

Olukoya, (2015). 'Language, Music, Education and National Development' *Awka Journal of Research in Music and the Arts*.vol.7 Department of Music, Namidi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Tleuova, A. Z., Baltymova, M. R., Niyazova, G. M., & Tektigul, Z. O. (2016). The World of Fantasy and the Trends in Modern Kazakh Fantastic Literature. *IEJME-Mathematics Education*, 11(6), 1591–1605.